

An empirical study to evaluate the student competency of vocational education

Rihab Wit Daryono¹, Muhammad Agphin Ramadhan², Nur Kholifah³, Fajar Danur Isnantyo⁴,
Muhammad Nurtanto⁵

¹Department of Islamic Education, Ponorogo State Islamic Institute, Ponorogo, Indonesia

²Department of Building Engineering Education, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia

³Department of Culinary and Fashion Education, Faculty of Engineering, Yogyakarta State University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

⁴Department of Vocational Engineering Education, Faculty of Engineering, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia

⁵Department of Mechanical Engineering Education, Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa University, Serang, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 29, 2021

Revised Dec 16, 2022

Accepted Jan 5, 2023

Keywords:

Architectural engineering

CB-SEM

Competency

Construction industry

Evaluation

Vocational education

ABSTRACT

The low work readiness of vocational education (VE) graduates is caused by a mismatch of competencies with job demands. The unemployment rate for VE graduates is increasing due to low competency mastery and job absorption. The purpose of this study is to determine the competency needs of architectural engineering graduates according to the current demand for the construction industry. The research sample consisted of 193 respondents consisting of VE teachers and practitioners from the construction industry in Indonesia. The Covariance-Based Structural Equation Modeling (CB-SEM) analysis is used for the evaluation of the structural models of architectural engineering competency demands. The results of the analysis test using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) show that the construct validity of the evaluation model is in a good category. The evaluation model testing met the statistical criteria of goodness of fit. The model substantially explains 89.75% of the various competencies that must be mastered by architectural engineering graduates and suitable for use in Indonesia and other countries.

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Corresponding Author:

Rihab Wit Daryono

Department of Islamic Education, Ponorogo State Islamic Institute

Ronowijayan, Siman, Ponorogo, East Java, Indonesia

Email: rihabwit.daryono@iainponorogo.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of science, technology, and information is very rapid which requires effective and efficient education [1], [2]. Education is an effort to grow and develop the potential possessed by students to become quality human resources [3], [4]. Competition makes the industry must have a strategy that can increase its competitiveness of the industry [5]–[7]. The competition in the vocational education (VE) curriculum is structured according to the suitability and needs of the industry and takes into account the development of students and the suitability of the type of work, social environment, national development needs developments in science, technology, and culture [8], [9]. Completion or improvement of education, especially VE is a form of harmonizing the development of the industry, technology, arts, and culture.

One of the visible problems is the limited employment opportunities due to the country's economic growth that has not met expectations, then the high unemployment rate for VE students [5], [9], [10], especially architectural engineering, indicates a competency gap between supply, and demand [6], [7], [11]. Rapid changes in the world of work as a result of the globalization of the world of work and the revolution in technology and various other scientific disciplines require anticipation and evaluation of the competencies

needed by the world of work [12], [13]. Evaluation is also important so that the world of higher education is not separated from the real world of work that exists in society. For this reason, VE must be responsive to changes that occur both locally and globally [8], [10]. To anticipate these changes, the VE program must be reviewed periodically to make adjustments in a direction that is more relevant to the situation and conditions.

Observations and interviews were conducted in the department of architectural engineering in Central Java, Indonesia. This department learns about construction and property technology work, especially in the implementation of construction and building planning. But in reality, from the programs that have been implemented in the world of education, there are several problems encountered so there is a mismatch between the education unit and the industrial construction. There are many graduates who have not found jobs and jobs that are not in accordance with their areas of expertise. Furthermore, the discrepancy in the content of competency material in schools with the demands of graduates' competence in the industry.

Furthermore, in the context of developing and implementing the curriculum, it is still limited to the school. There are several obstacles, namely the competencies needed by the industry have not been implemented in schools, and learning that emphasizes hard and soft skills simultaneously has not been maximized. Furthermore, schools have not maximized the application of all vocational competencies in learning theory and vocational practice. Such a curriculum is developed only from the school without involving industry to shape the material taught in the learning that will run. Curriculum development has not run optimally by involving all stakeholders including teachers, counselors, school committees, principals, and industry in the form of work meetings. So that the lack of school relations with the world of work causes the absorption of vocational graduates to work according to their fields to be very low.

This is as the results of research conducted by Daryono *et al.* [14] revealed that there is still a link and match gap between schools and industry so that it recommends several competencies of architectural engineering graduates including personality competencies, basic knowledge, and work skills. Furthermore, research by Wijayanti and Jaedun [15] revealed the development of architectural engineering technology in the world of work, especially in the construction industry which is recommended to be implemented in VE, it is necessary to support the curriculum and competencies according to the standards and requirements needed in the industry [7], [14]. Some of these standards, for example, are content standards, graduate competency standards, and standards for the world of work. Through the curriculum developed, it is hoped that VE can produce graduates who are professional and have competitive careers as workers in accordance with their fields of expertise. The curriculum in schools has a character that leads to the formation of vocational competencies contained in productive programs that are reliable and work in accordance with their fields of expertise which are based on normative and adaptive scientific bases to support vocational competencies that must be achieved. It is important for each educational unit to improve quality and design the best program so that it has an impact on graduates who are ready to work.

Therefore, very important to research competency evaluation to explore competency needs according to the demands and current standards in the construction industry. The purpose of this study is to determine the competency needs according to the demands of the world of work and the urgency of competence by industry needs and standards. Through this research, it is hoped that schools will be able to determine the urgency of current competencies in architectural engineering. As an evaluation of the development and preparation of the curriculum on architectural engineering competence. Furthermore, for the construction industry, sustainable collaboration can be established in the development of competencies and school curricula. This research is expected to be able to provide an evaluation to produce input to produce competencies that are by industry needs so that it can increase the absorption of architectural engineering students' graduates.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The research was conducted by conducting a survey in vocational education in Central Java of Indonesia and the construction service industry regarding the competencies that must be mastered for vocational school graduates in the architectural engineering department. The total sample was 193 respondents, consisting of 129 practitioners and trainers from 84 organizations in building construction companies and 64 VE teachers, from 11 VE in Central Java, Indonesia. Classification of construction service companies based on the main field of work, namely the building sector which consists of buildings, roads, bridges, and factory/workshops. Furthermore, the characteristics of the type of construction service business, the form of construction service business, employer profile, and organization category.

The use of Covariance-Based Structural Equation Modeling (CB-SEM) to estimate structural models based on strong theoretical studies to test the causality relationship between constructs and latent variables and measure the feasibility of the model and confirm it according to empirical data [3], [16]. The CB-SEM is used to analyze the relationship of the structural model which measures the dimensions between

architectural engineering competency factors that must be mastered by students and the competencies required by the current construction industry [3], [17]. Research is supported with the help of the Amos 22.00 program. Data were obtained from vocational school teachers, practitioners, and trainers in the construction industry who filled out a questionnaire through the Google Form. Conducting confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) testing to ensure model fit. The first stage is testing factor analysis by considering descriptive statistical analysis, data normality, multicollinearity between variable data, and data reduction. The upper threshold value for multicollinearity results is <0.90 [3], [16]. The steps used in this research method are checking whether the data meets multivariate normality or not. The reliability test used the construct reliability (CR >0.70 and AVE >0.50) [16], [18]. The evaluation model test using the CFA method aims to test the structural model between theory and empirical data [19].

3. RESULTS

Preliminary study testing was conducted to ensure that the data were normally distributed and multicollinearity analysis met each of the measurement constructs. After these two assumptions are met, then proceed with CFA testing to ensure Internal consistency reliability, and construct validity in the evaluation of measurement and structural architectural engineering competency models. The five competency items offered from the 35 competency items were determined to be invalid because they did not meet the normality assumption on the skewness and kurtosis values and the multicollinearity value. Competencies that do not meet the assumptions are five points, namely: GT3, KJJ1, EBK1, KUG4, and PKK1. All competency items that passed the preliminary analysis totaled 30 items reaching data normality (skewness and kurtosis values >1.96) [3], [20]. Furthermore, multicollinearity analysis revealed that the 10 competency measurement constructs had an intercorrelation matrix value between 0.252 to 0.756 (<0.90). These results indicate that the discriminant validity of each aspect of competence is acceptable. The overall instrument reliability results are in the acceptable category (CR values between 0.841 to 0.950 and AVE between 0.624 to 0.932).

3.1. Evaluation of structural model

This study examines and ensures the construct validity of two evaluation models to evaluate the graduates competencies according to the industry demands. The CFA test to prove and ensure the suitability and validity of the two models offered, covering 30 items of competency for architectural engineering graduates. Further testing of CFA is based on the univariate normality and multicollinearity analysis that have been met. Figure 1 and 2 represent two models for testing the validity of architectural engineering competencies according to the assessments of VE teachers, practitioners, and trainers in the industry.

Figure 1. First order model for evaluating the competency demands of architectural engineering education

Figure 2. Second order model for evaluating the competency demands of architectural engineering education

All model fit criteria from the goodness of fit parameter used for the assessment determination have met all existing threshold values. The first and second-order measurement model for evaluating student competence produces a suitable and acceptable fit parameter value, p -value, RMSEA (≤ 0.08); IFI, CFI, and TLI (≥ 0.90) qualifies as a fit model [16], [19]–[21]. The results of the second-order evaluation model test hypothesized very well based on the GoF criteria so the model is accepted as presented in Table 1. The analysis can be concluded that both models have met the construct validity test to evaluate competence and can be used to be applied in schools on the implementation of graduate competencies. The NFI value shows a value of 0.894 in the first order and 0.901 in the second order. This model substantially explains 89.75% of the various competencies that must be mastered by architectural engineering graduates.

Table 1. The results of two order models for evaluating the competence of architectural engineering students

Model fit criteria	Parameter goodness of fit	Threshold value	1st-order output	GF (1) MG (2)	2nd-order output	GF (1) MG (2)
Absolute fit measures	GF1	≥ 0.90	0.896	2	0.901	1
	AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.859	2	0.860	2
	RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.014	1	0.011	1
	RMR	≤ 0.10	0.015	1	0.014	1
Incremental fit measures	IFI	≥ 0.90	0.996	1	0.998	1
	TLI	≥ 0.90	0.994	1	0.997	1
	CFI	≥ 0.90	0.995	1	0.997	1
	NFI	≥ 0.90	0.894	2	0.901	1
Parsimonious fit measures	RFI	≥ 0.90	0.867	2	0.870	1
	PGFI	> 0.50	0.668	1	0.639	1
	PNFI	> 0.50	0.713	1	0.684	1
	PCFI	> 0.50	0.794	1	0.757	1

GF=Good fit, MG=Marginal fit

3.2. Hypothesis test: With the criteria t -value and p -value

The results of hypothesis testing obtained t -value > 1.96 and p -value < 0.05 , which indicates that the hypothesis is significant with the specified category. The sign of significance (***) indicates the p -value is less than 0.001. The value meets the criteria when the standard loading estimate (γ) is more than 0.5. Based on

Table 2, the hypothesis to determine the validity of the evaluation model developed to measure the achievement of student competencies is acceptable, because the t -value and p -value of all competency aspects meet the criteria in the constructed test and convergent validity.

Table 2. The validity test of the evaluation model to measure student competency achievement

Construct	Item	Estimate	Construct validity				Convergent validity	
			First-order		Second-order		First-order	Second-order
			t -value	p -value	t -value	p -value	Estimate (γ)	
KU	KU1	1.000					0.521	0.500
	KU2		5.902	***	5.543	***	0.500	0.529
	KU3		4.109	***	5.922	***	0.574	0.603
GT	GT1	1.000					0.736	0.763
	GT2		6.880	***	8.191	***	0.816	0.785
	MT1	1.000					0.500	0.613
MT	MT2		5.544	***	8.372	***	0.665	0.660
	MT3		5.765	***	9.608	***	0.781	0.766
	DKB1	1.000					0.890	0.977
DKB	DKB2		13.767	***	14.018	***	0.865	0.886
	DKB3		10.069	***	13.459	***	0.658	0.826
	TPTP1	1.000					0.560	0.500
TPTP	TPTP2		7.731	***	10.602	***	0.854	0.783
	TPTP3		7.960	***	10.414	***	0.760	0.762
	APLPIG1	1.000					0.755	0.752
APLPIG	APLPIG2		7.626	***	9.805	***	0.784	0.693
	APLPIG3		9.858	***	10.324	***	0.727	0.730
	APLPIG4		10.426	***	10.907	***	0.767	0.763
	KJJ2	1.000					0.813	0.516
KJJ	KJJ3		10.256	***	9.719	***	0.754	0.777
	KJJ4		10.073	***	8.607	***	0.751	0.818
	EBK2	1.000					0.636	0.500
EBK	EBK3		10.498	***	7.578	***	0.577	1.000
	EBK4		10.119	***	7.630	***	0.798	0.629
	KUG1	1.000					0.713	0.229
KUG	KUG2		6.181	***	4.910	***	0.831	0.701
	KUG3		7.536	***	4.981	***	0.824	0.815
	PKK2	1.000					0.808	0.500
PKK	PKK3		10.867	***	10.050	***	1.000	0.814
	PKK4		10.283	***	9.938	***	0.723	0.840

4. DISCUSSION

The General Competencies (KU) consists of three final indicators measuring architectural engineering competence, namely: have independence and responsibility in carrying out their job duties; have a curiosity to develop their skills on an ongoing basis; and hough to deal with work pressure, can work productively, and is beneficial to the work environment. The Basics and Technical Drawing (GT) consists of two final indicators competence, namely: drawing rules of symbols, notations, and dimensions on engineering drawings; drawing a pictorial (3D) projection. This competency indicator is in line with the results of research by Gil-Mastalerczyk [22]; Puškár, Vráblová, and Czafík [23]; and Zieliński [24] about technical drawing skills in concept drawing competencies and a basic drawing of building techniques.

The Basic Building Construction (DKB) consists of three final indicators measuring architectural engineering competence with the same results obtained by several researchers [25]–[28], namely i) Presenting the specifications and characteristics of wood, concrete, steel; ii) Carry out building construction work; and iii) Planning the use of materials and tools for construction work. The Engineering Mechanics Statics (MT) consists of three final indicators, namely: i) Calculating the balance of forces and the beam; ii) Calculation of moment, latitude, and normal forces in the application of building structures; and iii) Introduction and application of SAP 2000 software for structural planning. The results support previous studies [29], [30] on the evaluation of creative problem-solving abilities in building structure work competencies through interdisciplinary problem-based learning. The Land Measurement Techniques (TPT) consists of three final indicators, namely i) Carry out the operation of the water-pass and theodolite tools; ii) Performing measurement techniques and staking out; and iii) Performing maintenance techniques and checking the type of optics. These indicators of the competence of land measurement techniques support the results of the previous literatures [14], [30].

The Road and Bridge Construction (KJJ) consists of three final indicators measuring architectural engineering competence, namely presenting types of road and bridge drainage; and drawing views, sections, and details of roads and bridges (AutoCAD). In addition, other competencies are in line with research

findings by previous researchers [14], [23], [24], namely introduction and application of the Land Desktop application to create a cross-section of the road, and introduction and application of BIM software (Revit Architecture and ArchiCAD) for road and bridge construction planning. The Building Estimation and Costing (EBK) consists of three final indicators competence. These results support research by several researchers [29], [31], namely making progress from time schedule to determine accumulated work progress; application Microsoft Project to calculate the estimated cost of the building; and making reports on building, road, and bridge construction work. The results of the Utilities and Building Construction (KUG) construct are from the literature by [23], [28], [32]. This competency consists of three final indicators competence, namely i) Making detailed drawings of buildings (foundations, columns, beams, sloof, plates, roof trusses); ii) Making isometric drawings of clean and dirty water installations; and iii) Making electrical installation drawings (AutoCAD). In addition, evidence from the literature by Zieliński [24]; Ratajczyk-Piątkowska and Piątkowska [33] can be compared with our results.

The Software Application and Interior Design of Buildings (APL-PIG) consists of four final indicators measuring architectural engineering competence. These results confirm the results obtained by previous researches [14], [24] which found that the main competencies of architectural engineering graduates include presenting data on interior design work needs: i) Determining the interior decoration materials or ornaments and interior finishing materials; ii) Introduction and application of BIM software other than AutoCAD and Sketchup, namely Revit Architecture, ArchiCAD, and Tekla Structures; iii) Introduction and application to 3D rendering software, namely Lumion, Enscape, and V-Ray. The next competency indicators that are in line with evidence from the literature [22], [33] are drawing the acoustic design of the room and checking the results of the 3D rendering, can be compared with our results. The Entrepreneurship (PKK) consists of three final indicators measuring architectural engineering competence, namely: make product/service prototype; carry out product inspections in accordance with product criteria/operational standards; and creating media based on market segmentation promotion.

5. CONCLUSION

The contributions of this research are diverse and provide both theoretical and practical contributions. The first contribution is to reveal 10 aspects and 30 points of competence that must be mastered by students to work according to current construction industry standards. Evidence of construct validity and estimation of instrument reliability is acceptable. The second contribution is to reveal and confirm the level of construct validity in two multidimensional evaluation models to evaluate the competence of architectural engineering graduates. The third contribution is the performance evaluation model developed.

The evaluation model shows a strong predictive power to measure the competencies of architectural engineering graduates. This model substantially explains 89.75% of the various competencies that architectural engineering graduates must possess to work in the construction industry. Thus, the school can evaluate the mastery of student competencies and equip competencies to be ready to work. Adjustment of work competencies needs to be carried out in schools according to the needs of the work world. So that efforts to improve the quality of the competence of architectural engineering graduates through vocational education and the availability of graduates to work can be increased. Increase the achievement of competencies by the competencies expected by the industry.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Rihab Wit Daryono is a lecturer at the Institut Agama Islam Negeri Ponorogo, Indonesia. He had his master's degree in the Department of Technology and Vocational Education, Yogyakarta State University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia, in 2021. His research interest is vocational education, architectural and civil engineering education, education assessment and evaluation, technology, and vocational education, and TVET curriculum development. He can be contacted at email: rihabwit.daryono@iainponorogo.ac.id.

Muhammad Agphin Ramadhan is a lecturer and researcher at the Department of Building Engineering Education, Faculty of Engineering, Jakarta State University, Indonesia. His research interest is vocational education of building construction, media, and civil engineering learning materials, TVET curriculum development, competence, and skills in the civil engineering sector. He can be contacted at email: agphin@unj.ac.id.

Nur Kholifah is a lecturer at the Department of Clothing and Food Engineering, Yogyakarta State University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Research interest in the field of empowering vocational communities, learning methods, vocational teachers, and gamification. She can be contacted at email: nur.kholifah@uny.ac.id.

Fajar Danur Isnantyo is a lecturer and researcher at Department of Civil Engineering Education, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia. Research interest in the field of green TVET, vocational character building and project-based learning including teaching factory in vocational education. Member of Asian Academic Society for Vocational Education and Training (AASVET) University Road, Douliu City, Yunlin County 640, Taiwan (R.O.C). He can be contacted at email: isnantyo@staff.uns.ac.id.

Muhammad Nurtanto is a lecturer and researcher at the Department of Mechanical Engineering Education, Faculty of Teaching dan Training Education, University Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa, Banten, Indonesia. Now a day, his tenure in academic position is Lector/Assist. Prof. His research interest is teachers' professional identity, teacher learning, teacher knowledge, STEM Education, and TVET. He can be contacted at email: mnurtanto23@untirta.ac.id.